

Supplementary table S1: Research type, approach, title, keywords, authors, and year of publication of studies conducted in states of the Legal Amazon, published between 2000 and 2025, included in the present study.

Year	Type	Approach	Title	Keywords	Author(s)
2004	Book chapter	Ethnobotany	Ecology and management of patauá (<i>Oenocarpus bataua</i> Mart.) for fruit and oil production	Not Reported	Not reported
2009	Book chapter	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnoknowledge of medicinal plants in the São João do Tupé and Central communities (Sustainable Development Reserve of Tupé)	Medicinal Plants; Ethnobotany; Traditional Knowledge; Central Amazon; Economic Botany	Scudeller, V. V.; Veiga, J. B.; Araújo-Jorge, L. H.
2009	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Medicinal knowledge and plant utilization in an Amazonian coastal community of Marudá, Pará State (Brazil)	Ethnopharmacology; Ethnobotany; Medicinal Plants; Amazonian Coastal Community; Brazil	Marlia Coelho-Ferreira
2011	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used in the municipality of Vilhena, Rondônia	Natural Medicine; Amazon; Lamiaceae	Lima, R. A.; Magalhães, S. A.; Santos, M. R. A.
2012	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Knowledge and uses of babaçu (<i>Attalea speciosa</i> Mart. and <i>Attalea eichleri</i> (Drude) A. J. Hend.) among the Mebêngôkre-Kayapó of the Las Casas Indigenous Territory, Pará State, Brazil	Babassu Oil; Ethnospecies; Kayapó	González-Pérez, S. E.; Coelho-Ferreira, M.; Robert, P.; Garcés, C. L. L.
2013	Master's	Ethnoeconomics	Agrarian issues and peasant ethnoknowledge in the Pau Rosa community,	Way Of Life; Agrarian Issue;	Souza, S. do C.

	dissertation		Tarumã Mirim settlement, Manaus-AM	Ethnoknowledge; Medicinal Plants; Biodiversity	
2013	Full paper	Ethnopharmacology	Use of medicinal plants by residents of the municipality of Confresa, Vale do Araguaia-MT	Ethnoknowledge; Popular Knowledge; Araguaia Valley	Silva, E. F. S.; Ramos, P. R.; Araújo, M. L.; Martins, A. A.; Sena, M. B.
2014	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Medicinal plants used in Rondônia, Western Amazon, Brazil	Ethnobotany; Phytotherapy; Traditional Medicine	Santos, M. R. A.; Lima, M. R.; Oliveira, C. L. L. G.
2014	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Use of medicinal plants by visitors of the Santa Marcelina outpatient clinics, Porto Velho – RO	Popular Knowledge; Species; Preservation	Caetano, R. S.; Souza, A. C. R.; Feitoza, L. F.
2014	Article	Ethnoeconomics	Traditional practices of use and management of <i>Carapa</i> spp. (andiroba) in the Rio Jutaí Extractive Reserve, Amazonas, Brazil	Ethnoknowledge; Non-Timber Extractivism; Fishing; Pluriactivity	Calle, D. A. C.; Vieira, G.; Noda, H.
2014	Article	Ethnobotany	Traditional knowledge in a conservation unit located in a peri-urban floodplain environment: ethnobiology of andiroba (<i>Carapa guianensis</i> Aublet)	Local Ecological Knowledge; Environmental Perception; Amazon; Ethnobiology	Santos, M. N.; Cunha, H. F. A.; Lira-Guedes, A. C.; Gomes, S. C. P.; Guedes, M. C.
2014	Undergradu	Ethnopharmacology	Use and knowledge of medicinal plants: a case study around the “Zélia	Medicinal Plants; Health; Traditional	Borges, F. M. T.;

	ate thesis	y	Flexa da Silva” municipal school, Magalhães Barata municipality-PA	Knowledge	Santiago, N. B.
2015	Article	Ethnopharmacolog y	Medicinal flora of household gardens in Tangará da Serra, Mato Grosso, Brazil	Ethnobotany; Traditional Knowledge; Conservation; Management	Moreira, R. P. de M.; Neto, G. G.
2015	Article	Ethnobotany	Biodiversity and culture: a case study in the Apurinã Indigenous Territory (Brazil)	Biodiversity; Indigenous Community; Culture	Risso, L. C.
2015	Master’s dissertation	Ethnopharmacolog y	Ethnopharmacology and physiology of medicinal plants in the Tiningú quilombola community, Santarém, Pará, Brazil	Quilombola Communities; Amazon; Ethnobotany; Water Stress; Essential Oils	Carvalho, T. L. G. S.
2015	Article	Ethnopharmacolog y	Local knowledge and medicinal plants in the Sucuri community, Cuiabá, MT, Brazil	Plant Diversity; Ethnobotany; Ethnobotany Use; Folk Medicine	Gonçalves, K. G. G.; Pasa, M. C.
2015	Article	Ethnopharmacolog y	Medicinal and ritual plants commercialized at the 25 de Setembro market, Belém, Pará	Amazon; Plant Biodiversity; Ethnobotany; Open-Air Market	Carmo, T. N.; Lucas, F. C. A.; Lobato, G. J. M.; Gurgel, E. S. C.
2016	Book chapter	Ethnobotany	Ethnobotany of non-timber forest species in local communities of the Juruá Valley, Acre	Not Reported	Machado, F. S.
2016	Book chapter	Ethnobotany	Diversity and use of palms in the riparian forest of the Acre River	Not Reported	Farias, M. S.; Pereira, L. R.; Rodrigues, E.

2016	Book chapter	Ethnobotany	Agroforestry education for socioecological resilience in Amazonian Extractive Reserves	Not Reported	Freitas, R. R.; Haverroth, M.; Siviero, A.
2017	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Survey of medicinal plants used by users of three public health units in the municipality of Vilhena – RO	Medicinal Plants; Survey; Vilhena	Goebel, M. J. B.; Souza, A. C. R.
2018	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Popular beliefs: mystical and medicinal attributions to plants in the Cuiabá lowlands, Mato Grosso, Brazil	Health; Ethnobotany; Traditional Healers	Silva, R. J. B.; Oliveira, A. P. da S.; Froes, B.; Silva, R. L. F.
2018	Master's dissertation	Ethnobotany	Sateré-Mawé ethnoknowledge and the influence of environmental and anthropogenic factors on the distribution of forest species of ethnic interest	Anthropogenic Forests; Ethnobotany; Ethnoedaphology; Ethnopedology; Indigenous Forest Management	Aguiar, Olivia Beatriz Moraes Dias de
2018	Article	Ethnobotany	Ethnobotanical survey of the medicinal plant <i>Aloe vera</i> L. in the São Gonçalo Beira Rio community, Cuiabá, MT	Traditional Knowledge; Riverside Communities; Phytotherapeutics	Messias, A.; Corillo, R.; Bio, B.; Valee Diel; Baldini, R.
2019	Master's dissertation	Ethnoeconomics	Informational practices related to the knowledge and practices of the herbal vendors of Ver-o-Peso: an interdisciplinary analysis	Herbal Vendors; Ver-O-Peso; Traditional Knowledge; Information Science	Dantas, C. F. N.
2019	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnobotany of medicinal flora in household gardens in the Mamangal community, Igarapé-Miri, PA	Plants Cultivated In Household Gardens; Traditional Medicinal Plant	Dos Santos, E. Q.; Costa, J. F. S.; Pereira, M. G. S.;

				Knowledge; Local Phytopharmacopoeia	Costa, J. M.; De Sousa, R. L.
2019	Undergraduate thesis	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnoknowledge of medicinal plants cultivated in household gardens in the Mamangal Grande community, Meruú River, Igarapé-Miri, Pará	Mamangal Community; Plants Cultivated In Household Gardens; Traditional Medicinal Plant Knowledge	Dos Santos, E. Q.
2019	Article	Ethnoeconomics	Andiroba oil: extraction, commercialization, and traditional uses in the Mamangal community, Igarapé-Miri, Pará	Medicinal Oil; Production Chain; Oil Extractors; <i>Carapa Guianensis</i>	Sousa, R. L.; Almeida, B. B.; Da Silva, R. P.; De Albuquerque, L. C. S.; Cordeiro, Y. E. M.
2020	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants used in the Buritizinho village, Chapadinha – MA	Medicinal Plants; Phytotherapy; Traditional Communities	Silva, T. V.; Brito, M. V.; Lopes, B. L.; Silva, M. S. C.; Costa, G. N.; Santos, L. L. M.; Silva, J. S.; Sousa, F. S.
2020	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnopharmacological survey of medicinal plants used in the municipality of Tocantinópolis – TO	Medicinal Plants; Popular Knowledge; Ethnobotany	Santos, K. M. S.; Martins, M. L.; Nascimento, G. N. L.

2021	Article	Ethnoeconomics	Study of the stability of a cosmetic emulsion with moisturizing cream potential for the treatment of cutaneous xerosis using babaçu (<i>Orbignya phalerata</i> Martius) oil	Babassu Oil (<i>Orbignya Phalerata</i> Martius); Emulsion; Cosmetics	Júnior, E. R.; Costa, M. C. P. C.; Silva, A. C. L. N.; Sales, J. S.; Pereira, F. S.; Santos, E. P.
2021	Article	Ethnobotany	Ethnobotany and Indigenous Traditional Knowledge in Brazil: Contributions to Research in Ecopsychology	Plants; Ecopsychology; Javaé People; Brazil; Traditional Knowledge	Tito, M. C. P. S.; Silva, J. C.
2021	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnobotany of medicinal plants used in the treatment of skin wounds in two rural communities of the Lower Tocantins region, Amazon, Brazil	Plants With Wound-Healing Potential; Skin Wounds; Amazonian Medicinal Plants	Ribeiro, D. S.; Sousa, A. C. R.; Maia, A. A. B.; Silva, S. G.; Costa, J. M.; Fonseca, D. J. S.; Pereira, M. G. S.; Cordeiro, Y. E. M.
2021	Undergraduate thesis	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnoknowledge and the use of medicinal plants by residents of the Santa Rosa village in São Bento, Maranhão	Traditional Knowledge; Scientific Knowledge; Folk Medicine; Rural Community; Baixada Maranhense	Penha, D. A. de J. A.
2021	Undergraduate thesis	Ethnobotany	Medicinal plants: a proposal for chemistry teaching in the Amazonian context, valuing popular, school, and academic knowledge	Medicinal Plants; Popular Knowledge; School Knowledge;	Bruno Oliveira dos Santos

				Academic Knowledge; Chemistry	
				Teaching	
2022	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnobotanical knowledge of medicinal plants used by residents of a riverside municipality in the interior of Amazonas State, Brazil	Ethnobotany; Medicinal Plants; Phytotherapeutics	Silva, Z. G.; Leone, F. R.; Cella, W.
2022	Book chapter	Ethnopharmacology	Traditional female knowledge and medicinal plants: a case study in the Nossa Senhora do Carmo neighborhood, Curuá, Pará, Brazil	Not Reported	Maciel, E. C.; Patrícia, C. de O.
2022	Master's dissertation	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnobotany, sustainable cultivation, and therapeutic use of medicinal plants: cultural health habits and quality of life in quilombola communities of the Lower Amazon	Culture; Collective Health; Medicinal Plants	Ribeiro, A. C. S.
2022	Book chapter	Ethnobotany	Ethnoknowledge and Northeastern migrants: a case study in the Boa Fé community, Mojuí dos Campos	Not Reported	Santos, E. da S.; Patrícia, C. de O.
2022	Master's dissertation	Ethnobotany	Useful plants in the Jacarequara quilombola community, municipality of Santa Luzia do Pará – PA	Ethnoknowledge; Ethnobotany; Traditional Populations; Cultural Diversity	Silva, E. J. C.
2023	Full paper	Ethnobotany	Dialogue between traditional knowledge and scientific contributions: an experience report in agroecological household gardens in the Lower Tocantins	Agroecology; Education; Local Knowledge; Mapping; Diversity	Rodrigues, E. T. R. T.; Santos, S. S.; Sarges Dias, T.; Silva Lima, V.
2023	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Medicinal plants in peri-urban household gardens: spaces for biodiversity	Amazon; Communities;	Souza, C. N. M.; Silva, J.

	y	valorization in São Miguel do Guamá, Pará	Ethnobotany; Traditional Knowledge	P. J.; Santos, J. A.; Lucas, F. C. A.	
2025	Article	Ethnopharmacology	Ethnoknowledge associated with the use of medicinal plants by rural communities in Peixoto de Azevedo, Mato Grosso	Traditional Communities; Conservation; Ethnobotany; Future Generations	Carbolim, R. L.; Silva, V. C. P.; Arruda, R.; Cavalheiro, L.; Battirola, L. D.

Source: Authors.